

Identification of Vanadium by using a Schiff Base derived from 2-Furfuraldehyde and *p*-Aminophenylmercaptoacetic Acid†

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Among the few reagents proposed for the identification of vanadium¹, mention may be made of hydrogen peroxide, α -benzoinoxime, 8-hydroxyquinoline, diaminobenzidine and based on catalytic oxidation of aniline. Some of the methods are subject to many interferences, less sensitive and require heating also. Recently, *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid has been used as a new diazotisable amine for the spectrophotometric determination of nitrite², cerium³ and chromium⁴ based on azo dye formation. In the present communication, a new Schiff base derived from 2-furfuraldehyde and

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p-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid has been used as a reagent for the identification of vanadium.

Results and Discussion

The structure of the Schiff base is supported by elemental analysis, ir spectra and negative test for a free amino group. The elemental analyses data were found to be in agreement with those of the calculated values. The Schiff base showed ir bands at 1490 and 1510 (furan oxygen)⁶ and 1600 cm^{-1} (C=N) indicating that aldehyde has condensed with *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid⁶. The solution of the Schiff base failed to give positive test for diazotisation-coupling reactions².

Vanadium gives a bluish violet colour with the Schiff base in the pH range 1.0–3.5; pH~2 was found to give maximum colour intensity. A 0.01 ml of KCl-HCl buffer solution (pH~2) and 0.01 ml of 0.2% Schiff base reagent were found to be optimum. The bluish violet vanadium Schiff base complex starts appearing within 10 min. The colour was found to be stable for 1 h.

The effect of foreign ions that often accompany vanadium in diverse geological samples was examined by carrying out identification of 0.01 ml of 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of vanadium on a spot plate in the presence of each of these ions. The tolerance limits (ppm) of foreign ions were found as follows: Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cr^{VI} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} , UO_2^{II} , Cu^{II} , Al^{III} , Sr^{II} , Ba^{II} , Se^{IV} , Pb^{II} , Th^{IV} , Nb^{V} , Ta^{V} and Be^{II} (100 each); Ce^{IV} (50), Mo^{VI} and Fe^{III} (20). Fluoride, chloride, sulphate, nitrate, citrate, oxalate, phosphate and tartrate did not interfere. Higher concentration of Fe^{II} gave positive interference. The positive interference due to Fe^{II} could be prevented by the addition of phosphoric acid or fluoride ion. The interference due to Ti^{IV} , Bi^{III} , Zr^{IV} and W^{VI} could be masked by using tartaric acid.

Simplicity, temperature-independence, sensitivity and selectivity are the advantages of the proposed method.

Experimental

p-Aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid (98% purity, Evans) and 2-furfuraldehyde (Merck-Schunhardt) were used as such. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade. A stock solution of vanadium (5 mg ml^{-1}) was prepared from ammonium metavanadate and standardised titrimetrically⁷ and diluted to give a standard solution containing 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of

vanadium. Solution of other elements were prepared by dissolving suitable salts in water or dilute hydrochloric acid. An aqueous solution of Schiff base reagent (FAPMA; 0.2%, w/v) was prepared. Buffer solution (pH~2) was prepared by adding 0.2 *M* KCl (12.5 ml) to 0.2 *M* HCl (3.25 ml) and diluting the solution to 50 ml. Ir spectra were recorded on a Carl Zeec M-80 spectrophotometer.

2-Furfuraldehyde-4-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid Schiff base (FAPMA): 2-Furaldehyde (5.26 ml) was added gradually to a solution of *p*-aminophenylmercaptoacetic acid (1 mol, 100 ml) in 1 *M* HCl with vigorous stirring when the solution turned dark reddish and started precipitating within 10 min. The resulting mixture was heated and allowed to stand overnight. The resulting reddish brown solid was washed with alcohol and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride, (80%) (Found: C, 59.9; H, 4.2; N, 5.2. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_3\text{S}$ calcd. for: C, 59.8; H, 4.2; N, 5.4%).

Procedure: A drop (0.01 ml) of the test solution was treated on a spot plate with KCl-HCl buffer (pH~2; 0.01 ml) and a 0.2% aqueous solution of the Schiff base reagent (0.01 ml). A bluish violet colour appeared within 10 min, indicating the presence of vanadium. Identification limit was 0.2 μg vanadium and the limit of dilution was 1 : 50000.

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References

1. F. FEIGL, "Spot Tests in Inorganic Analysis", 5th. ed., 1970, Elsevier, New York, pp. 123-127.
2. P. K. TARAFDER and D. P. S. RATHORE, *Analyst*, 1988, **113**, 1073; D. P. S. RATHORE and P. K. TARAFDER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 185; 1990, **67**, 231; *Acta Ciencia Indica*, 1990, **16** (P), 21.
3. D. P. S. RATHORE and P. K. TARAFDER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 179.
4. D. P. S. RATHORE and P. K. TARAFDER, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1992, **257**, 129.
5. P. CHATTERJEE, H. K. DUGGAL, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 550.
6. N. K. DUTTA and H. C. CHAKDER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **32**, 2303; L. D. FREDRICKSON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1964, **36**, 1349.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., Longman, London, 1961, p. 309.